

PROSPER

A micro-game about yesterday, today and tomorrow

Prosper: DiBL edition facilitator guide

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Main guide

Intro

Prosper is a facilitated, collaborative educational strategy game, where participants take on the roles of different interest groups, from community organizations and politicians to technology developers and the private sector, all working together to try to solve a series of problems, and ultimately work towards a more sustainable and equitable world.

Prosper is structured around the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, which serve as the fundamental mechanical building blocks of the game. It thus serves as an ideal learning tool for exploring how the Sustainable Development Goals interact with each other, and the many different kinds of solutions that are bringing the world closer to fulfilling these goals, in an interactive and engaging way.

Target audience: Secondary education or above

Duration: ~90 minutes / 2x50 minutes

Technical equipment: A personal device per participant (smart phone, laptop or tablet), and a device (laptop recommended) for the facilitator to run the case from, ideally connected to a large screen or projector

Learning objectives:

- Learn about the Sustainable Development Goals
- Put yourself in the shoes of different stakeholders
- Think strategically about risk management and the value of short term vs. long term solutions
- Practice arguing your position, negotiation, and compromise

Overview

The game follows a mostly linear structure, taking players through 8 consecutive rounds, each of which presents players with a specific problem they must try to solve (this is covered in detail in “Rounds”).

Facilitator vs. participant screen

The case is split into two parts - the *facilitator screen* and the *participant screen*. Since no participants have joined the session yet (see “Logging in”), let’s concentrate on the facilitator screen first.

Facilitator screen

This is the screen you, the facilitator, will be using while running the case. The facilitator screen has most of the information participants need, and is where the game mainly “takes place”. When participants aren’t making choices or interacting directly, they’ll mostly be focused on the facilitator screen. We recommend using a large screen or projector, so all participants can easily see the facilitator screen at the same time.

In some ways, the facilitator screen functions like a regular slide show or presentation - it has mainly static elements, such as images and text, as well as videos and animations.

Participant screen

Once one or more participants have joined the session, they’ll have their own screen on their device, which they’ll use to interact with the game. Whenever participants have to make a choice during the game - when voting on a solution (see “Solving problems”), or picking teams (see “teams”) - they’ll do so on their devices. Each facilitator page has a specific, corresponding participant page attached to it. When participants don’t need to interact with the case directly, their participant page will generally be the “Stay tuned” page.

Setting up a session

To set up a session, use the “start a session” link on the open access platform. This will open a new window or tab in the browser you’re using, and start a new session of the case. You can try this out before running your first real session with participants.

Logging in

This is the page where participants use their own device to log in and access the case, by going to a specific website. This can be done in the following ways:

- Scanning the QR code on the page with a device capable of scanning QR codes. On most modern smartphones, looking at the QR code in the phone’s camera app will scan it, giving the user a link to the webpage.
- Using the participant link (the address underneath the QR code, i.e. dibl.eu/styg) to open the participant page. This is the suggested solution for participants using a laptop or other device which cannot scan QR codes.
- As the facilitator, you can share the link with participants via email, chat, or any other appropriate option. However, only do this once you’ve started the session! To link to the specific session you’re running, the address is unique to that session, and is only created once that session has begun.
- Participants can also enter the short web address manually into their browser themselves.

Once a participant has logged in, they will see the “Stay tuned” page on their device.

On the login page, you’ll see a counter showing the number of participants who have logged in. Checking that number against the number of participants in the room, you can verify that all participants have successfully logged in before moving on.

What if some participants join the session later?

You don't have to go back to the login page to allow more participants to join. By clicking the QR code icon in the bottom left corner of the facilitator screen, you can bring the QR code and session address back up at any time. New participants can use those to join, in the same ways we covered above.

What if some participants have to leave early?

You don't need to do anything special for participants to leave - they can just close the browser window they're using for the session, and the facilitator will stop tracking them as participants in the session. However, if all members of a team leave the session early, that team will then not be able to pick solutions, which will make the game harder. Therefore, if you know ahead of time that some participants will have to leave early, put them in teams with others who will stay until the end (see "Teams").

What if some participants are not able to access the session, or lose their connection to the session?

This is covered on the "Technical problems" page.

Teams

The first choice players are asked to make is to join one of the game's five teams:

- **Technology Developers**
- **Public Policy Analysts**
- **Community Coordinators**
- **Business Council**
- **International Collaborators**

Each team will have access to different solutions during the game. However, *all teams work together to try to solve the problems presented to them* - the game is fully cooperative, and players should share all information with each other and try to make their decisions together.

Recommendations for selecting teams

Each team can have any number of members, from one per team to as many as makes sense in the context.

We generally recommend playing with 4 or 5 different teams if possible, even with a smaller group of players. The more different teams are in play, the more of the “puzzle” players will be able to see, and the more different perspectives they will be able to bring to bear on a problem. Be aware that the number of teams in play will affect the *balance* of the game in a number of ways (see “Balance” at the end for details). This is not something that players need to think about. *You need at least 2 different teams for the game to work.*

As facilitator, you can choose whether to decide for players which teams to put them in (although they will have to make the actual selection themselves on their own devices), or let participants decide for themselves. Try to have roughly equal numbers of players in each of the active teams.

We recommend that participants join teams that in some way reflect their interests or occupation. This does not mean that you have to be an engineer to join the Technology Developers team, or a business leader to join the Business Council. Think creatively about how participants' occupations or interests could inform their team affiliation - perhaps someone with a farming background might lean more towards practical, technological solutions, making them a good fit for Technology Developers, and someone working a service job might be more interested in the types of social solutions offered by Community Coordinators or Public Policy Analysts. If you have time, consider having this discussion with the participants at the start,

Switching teams

Halfway through the game, after the first four rounds, players will have the opportunity to change their teams. Here, we recommend keeping the same *number* of teams in play, but having players rotate which teams they're each a part of, to see a different perspective. If you don't have all five teams in play, this is also a good opportunity to bring in one of the teams that have not been in play at all so far - have players discuss together which of the teams in play so far they would like to switch out, and which of the teams not in play so far they would like to bring in as a replacement.

Explaining the rules

After players have picked their teams, the game navigates to a brief rules explanation, which is a short summary of the full rules laid out in this facilitation guide. This explanation is reproduced here:

“In this game, you play as different teams, working together to solve a series of problems, and make the world a better place. The game has 8 rounds, each with a different problem you have to try and solve together. Each team has access to different types of solutions, so you will have to coordinate and work together to have the best chance of success.

The game is structured around the 17 Sustainable Development Goals - or SDGs, for short. Each SDG represents a goal you are working towards - from No Poverty to Affordable and Clean Energy. Each problem you'll face will relate to some of the SDGs (we call those its “impacted SDGs”), which means three things:

- *Solving* the problem means you *gain progress* towards its impacted SDGs
- *Failing* to solve the problem means you *lose progress* towards its impacted SDGs
- Your progress on a problem's impacted SDGs make it easier or harder to solve it. That means that, if you're facing a problem related to the goal of No Poverty, if you've already gained a lot of progress towards that goal, you'll have a better chance of solving it, but if that goal is further away, you'll have a *worse* chance.

When facing a problem, each team gets three different solutions to pick from, and picks the one they want to implement by voting on their devices. There are two different types of solutions: *short term solutions*, and *long term solutions*. A long term solution gives some progress towards one or more SDGs, not all of which are necessarily relevant for the current problem. A short term solution does not give progress towards any SDGs, but directly increases your *chance of success* of solving the problem. A team will always have access to one short term and two long term solutions for each problem. We'll talk more about this in a moment, when facing our first problem.

Once all teams have picked their solutions, the game *rolls a die* to see if the problem was solved or not. This represents the fact that there are no guaranteed solutions. It's not completely random, however - we will add a *modifier* to that roll, based on the status of the impacted SDGs and the short term solutions we implemented. If the outcome is high enough, we'll have solved the problem, and gain further progress on the impacted SDGs - if not, we'll have failed to solve the problem, and *lose* progress on those SDGs. We'll cover exactly how this works during the first round.

Once we've solved, or failed to solve, the problem, we move on to the next. We will have to face many different kinds of problems along the way, and may encounter other surprises as well. Let's get to it!”

We recommend that you read this explanation aloud, or have one or more players do so. If players have questions before you begin, you can answer these immediately, but we recommend using the first round as a kind of trial run, explaining the rest of the rules in detail step by step.

For ease of reference, here are some excerpts from later parts of the guide that you can use for this purpose:

SDGs in detail (for when players are first picking their solutions):

Each SDG has a *status* (the number shown above the SDG icon), and a *progress* (the number shown below). An SDG's *status* represents the long-term state of this SDG in the world, and is hard to change. Its *progress* represents how close its status is to going up or down - progress is shown as X / Y , where X is current progress, and Y is the number this SDG would need to hit to increase its status by 1 (at which point Y is subtracted from progress). If an SDG's progress goes below 0, its status decreases by 1 (at which point Y is added to progress).

Rolling the dice (right before rolling the dice)

It works like this:

- You now have to make a dice roll.
- The number rolled will then be *modified* in the following ways:
 - Each short term solution chosen adds +1 to the roll, up to a point
 - The *status* of each *impacted SDG* is added to (or subtracted from!) the roll
 - The total added to (or subtracted from) the roll is called the *modifier*.
- The outcome, or *modified number*, is then compared to your *target number*. If you hit or exceed your target number, the problem is solved - if you don't you fail to solve the problem.

In the first round, each team has the option of *changing their mind* after first picking their preferred solution. This is to give players a chance to make some initial decisions quickly, even if they do not fully understand the game's rules, and then see the outcome of those decisions. If you sense that some players have a hard time grasping the rules initially, suggest that each team just try and pick the solution they think sounds best for now, and move on. Players will then be shown the effects of their decisions, and their chance of success. Each team then has to decide if they want to keep the solution they picked, or choose a different one. At this point, you can prompt players to all come together across teams, and coordinate as a group which solutions they think will be most effective. *Be aware that this option is only provided for the first round.*

If this is your first time playing the game or reading this facilitation guide, we recommend that you familiarize yourself with the rest of this guide before playing.

Setup

Before you begin playing, you as the facilitator will be asked to make two choices affecting the game's setup. The impact of each of these decisions is outlined in more detail in later chapters.

The consequences of success and failure:

This choice is made on the page where players choose their teams. Consequences are set to either Normal or Large, for both success and failure independently. Setting success to Large and failure to Normal will result in an easier game, and setting success to Normal and failure to Large will result in a hard game. Setting both to Normal or Large will result in a balanced game, with Large making the game more dynamic. These can be adjusted halfway through, after the first 4 rounds, when players can also change their teams.

We recommend starting with both success and failure at Large, potentially adjusting either to Normal halfway through, to adjust the difficulty to the group. See "Success and failure" for more on what the consequences are in detail, and "Balance" for how the number of active teams affect consequences as well.

Whether to randomize the starting SDG setup:

This is chosen on the Rules page, right after selecting teams. If you choose not to randomize, all SDGs will start at the same starting progress (determined by the number of active teams, as described in "Balance"). If you do choose to randomize, the starting progress will be adjusted up or down for 8 of the 17 SDGs in total, with 4 starting higher than the rest, and 4 starting lower. The total amount of starting progress across all SDGs will still be the same - the amount of progress lost on the 4 low SDGs equals the amount gained on the 4 high SDGs. Which ones are picked to start high vs. low is random, so players might have a harder or easier time in the first few rounds if you choose to randomize, depending on which ones get randomized up or down. We recommend randomizing the starting SDG setup - we find it makes the world feel more dynamic and real, with players coming into a world already in motion. You might choose not to do this if you think a group of players will have an especially hard time following the game's rules and complexity.

Structure

Rounds

The game plays out over 8 rounds, which present 8 different problems for players to try to solve together. Each round follows the same gameplay structure. After every other round, before starting the next one, there are special “world events” – these are in some ways similar to the regular rounds, but use different mechanics. We will cover regular round gameplay first, and world events second.

Each round consists of the following pages:

Problem introduction

Here, the problem players are dealing with during this round is introduced, and the Sustainable Development Goals impacted by the problem are outlined (see “Impacted SDGs”).

Choosing solutions

Here, each team chooses a solution to implement, trying to address the problem (see “Solving problems”).

Feedback

Here, we see the solutions picked by each team, and their effect on the players' chance of success for solving the problem, and on the world as a whole.

Rolling dice

Here, players roll the dice to determine whether or not their solutions successfully solve the problem (see "Rolling the dice").

Outcome

Here, players see the outcome of the dice roll, and its effect on the world, positive or negative (see "Success and failure").

Problem debrief

Here, the narrative outcome is delivered as text, before players move on to the next problem.

As mentioned above, in between some rounds, players also experience special World Events, which follow a different structure (see "World Events").

SDGs

The game is about players on different teams working together to solve problems relating to the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Each SDG has a *status* (the number shown above the SDG icon), and a *progress* (the number shown below). An SDG's *status* represents the long-term state of this SDG in the world, and is hard to change. Its *progress* represents how close its status is to going up or down - progress is shown as X / Y , where X is current progress, and Y is the number this SDG would need to hit to increase its status by 1 (at which point Y is subtracted from progress). If an SDG's progress goes below 0, its status decreases by 1 (at which point Y is added to progress).

Example:

SDG 1: No Poverty is at 6/8 progress, and SDG 2: Zero Hunger is at 1/8 progress. Both are at status 0. Something happens that gives +3 to SDG 1, and -2 to SDG 2. This raises SDG 1 to a status of 1, with progress (towards status 2) now at 1/8, and lowers SDG 2 to a status of -1, with a progress of 7/8.

Impacted SDGs

In each round, there is a number of *impacted SDGs* relating to the round's problem, from 2 to 4, depending on the problem. The fact that an SDG impacts a problem means three things:

- Its status will directly affect the players' *success chance* when dealing with that problem
- If players solve the problem, they will *gain progress* on the impacted SDGs of that problem
- If players *fail* to solve the problem, they will *lose progress* on the impacted SDGs of that problem

A problem does not impact all SDGs equally - this means that solving the problem, or failing to solve it, will have more of an effect on some SDGs than others (see "Success and failure"). All impacted SDGs affect the *success chance* equally, though (see "Rolling the dice").

Solving problems

Now we come to what players are actually doing in the game. Each round, after being presented with the problem and its impacted SDGs, players will have to choose *solutions* to implement – one for each team in play. Each team has access to 3 unique solutions for each problem, and chooses one of these to implement.

There are two different types of solutions: *short term solutions* and *long term solutions*. These affect the players' chance of solving the problem in different ways, explained in more detail in "Rolling the dice" below. A team always has access to one short term solution, and two different long term solutions, for a specific problem.

On the Choose solutions page for each round, players use their devices to vote on which of the three solutions available to their team they prefer to implement. At the top of the page, players have three buttons, each of which corresponds to a potential solution their team could implement. The button itself has the name of the solution, as well as a summary of which SDGs it affects. They click the button for their preferred solution to vote for it. They can change their mind until the facilitator moves on to the next page – they simply have to click the button of the selected solution first, to deselect it, before clicking on another solution to vote for that one instead. The facilitator can track how many players have voted for a solution within each team, to track whether everyone has voted.

Rolling the dice

Whether or not players succeed in solving a problem in Prosper is decided with a single, dramatic *dice roll*, after teams have picked their solutions. This is to represent the unpredictability and volatility of actually solving long term problems in the world. However, it's not completely random: the players' *chance of success* is affected by the solutions they choose for that round - and by their choices in *previous* rounds, and whether or not they solved those problems.

It works like this:

- After each team has chosen their solution, and it has been implemented, the players will have to make a dice roll.
- The number rolled will then be *modified* in the following ways:
 - Each short term solution chosen adds +1 to the roll, up to a point (see "Short term solutions" below).
 - The *status* of each *impacted SDG* is added to (or subtracted from!) the roll
 - The total added to (or subtracted from) the roll is called the *modifier*.
- The outcome, or *modified number*, is then compared to the players' *target number*. If players hit or exceed their target number, the problem is solved - if they don't they fail to solve the problem (see "Success and failure" below).
- The "size"/number of sides on the of the die, as well as the target number, are determined by the number of teams in play (see "Balance" below)

See "Example of a round" for a detailed example of the dice mechanic.

Solutions in detail

Short term solutions:

Give +1 to the modifier for the current problem, directly increasing chance of success. However, *there is a maximum number of short term solutions* that can effectively impact a given problem. If 5 teams are in play, the maximum number of effective short term solutions for a given problem is 2 (see “Balance” below for a full breakdown of maximum effective short term solutions by number of teams). *This number is not shown to players* – at the start of the game, they will not know exactly how many short term solutions they can effectively use per round, or if that number changes from round to round (it does not). *We recommend that you as the facilitator make players aware that there is a limit to how many short term solutions they can effectively use per round* – but that you do not tell them the exact number.

Short-term

Regulate Coastal Development

Implement stricter regulations on coastal development to reduce pollution and runoff that harm coral reefs.

+1
success chance

Long term solutions:

Give progress to two or more SDGs, thereby potentially affecting success chance for the current problem, as well future problems. This way, players can try to gain enough progress on the impacted SDGs of the current problem to raise their status – but depending on their initial progress going into the round, and the solutions available to the different teams, they will not be able to prioritize all impacted SDGs, and will have to coordinate their solutions to have the most impact.

A long term solution will always provide a total of +4 progress to one or SDGs, some of which impact the current problem, and some of which do not. Some long term solutions have a smaller effect on a larger number of SDGs, such as +1 to 4 different SDGs, while others are more targeted, such as giving +3 to one SDG, and +1 to another. In rounds 3 onwards, a small number of solutions *lower* progress for an SDG, while increasing others more significantly. The progress from these still add up to 4, such as a solution giving +4 to one SDG, +2 to another, and -2 to a third one, signifying the tradeoffs associated with complex or controversial solutions.

Long-term

Educate on Sustainable Fishing and Reef Conservation

Conduct educational programs for local communities on sustainable fishing practices and the importance of coral reef conservation.

2 Zero Hunger	4 Quality Education	11 Sustainable Cities and Communities	14 Life Below Water
+1	+1	+1	+1

Success and failure

After rolling the dice, and determining whether or not players successfully solved the problem, players receive the *consequences* of the outcome. If they succeeded, they *gain progress* on all the impacted SDGs of that problem - if they fail, they *lose progress* on the impacted SDGs. This might result in some SDGs either gaining or losing *status*, if they cross the threshold (see “SDGs”).

The amount of progress gained or lost is not the same for all impacted SDGs - some are more impacted by success or failure than others. The exact consequences of success and failure are not known to players before resolving a problem - they only know which SDGs will be impacted, not how much they’ll be impacted.

The consequences of success and failure are set by the facilitator during setup, as either Normal or Large (see “Setup”). If both are set to the same, the negative impact on each SDG resulting from failing a given problem is the same as the positive impact on each SDG for that problem in reverse.

The effect on each impacted SDG differs depending on the total number of impacted SDGs for a problem. These range from 2 to 4. The *total impact* is always the same (2 * number of teams, if set to Normal, and 3 * number of teams, if set to Large) - this total impact is then distributed among the impacted SDGs, unevenly, depending in their priority. This means that a problem with only two impacted SDGs will have a larger effect on those SDGs (positive or negative) than a problem with four impacted SDGs, since the total amount of progress gained or lost from a problem is always the same.

After receiving the consequences, players either go to the next problem, which follows the same procedure described above, or go to a World Event, before moving on to the next problem.

Example of a round

In this example, four teams (Technology Developers, Public Policy Analysts, Business Council and International Collaborators) enter the third round, and have to deal with the problem of Plastic Choked Oceans, which impacts SDGs 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) and 14 (Life Below Water). Because they managed to solve a previous problem related to life below water, 14 is already at +1 status at the start of the round, meaning the players start the round with a +1 modifier. Both 12 and 14 are also already 4/8 progress towards their next status increase.

The teams discuss their options, and decide to prioritize SDG 12 - they can immediately see that they have more solutions among them that do something about 12, and 14 is already at +1 status. But then, International Collaborators realize they have a solution this gives +4 to 12: Introduce Extended Producer Responsibility. This one solution would effectively bring SDG 12 all the way up to its next status (it starts the round at 4/8 progress), and it *also* gives +2 to 14. The only downside is that it gives -2 to 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure). The teams discuss this, but agree that this solution is so strong that they *have* to take it - they'll have to deal with the consequences for SDG 9 later. This leaves the other teams. At first, they discuss having everyone else pick their short term solutions, but since they don't know exactly how many short term solutions will be effective, they instead decide to see if they can actually get SDG 14 all the way up to a +2 status. It turns out every other team has a solution available giving +1 progress to 14, so if they all go with those go with that, they'll get 14 to +2 status, which would give them a total modifier of +3 - not bad at all. Business Council proposes to instead go for a short term solution, since they only need +2 progress to 14 in total to get the status increase. Everyone else agrees - now it's just a question of which of the available solutions giving +1 to 14 they prefer. Public Policy Analysts only have one solution that works here: Implement Deposit Return Schemes, which gives another +2 to 12 as well, and +1 to 11. They go with that. Technology Developers have two solutions available that would work: Implement Microplastic Filtration Systems, which gives a nice bump to SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation) and a bit to 3 (Good Health and Well-Being) - and Invest in Waste-to-Energy Technology, which gives +2 to 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), +2 to 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure), and the +1 to 14 they were looking for. It does give -1 to 13 (Climate Action), but they're actually doing okay on that, so they'll take the hit. The +2 to 9 evens out the drawback from International Collaborator's original solution, so that's perfect. Business Council does go with their short term solution. Each team votes for the solutions they picked, and when everything's counted up, the result is a whopping +4 modifier - *incredible*.

The players will now roll the dice. With four teams, they're rolling an 8-sided die, trying to hit a 7. Slim odds, if didn't have a strong modifier. But with a +4 to their roll, they just have to roll a 3 or higher, which means their success chance is 75%. They roll a 4 - a success! This results in +4 progress to SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), and +8 progress to SDG 14 (Life Below Water). This will help them with future problems impacted by these SDGs. Not bad at all.

World Events

World Events are special events that happen in between some rounds, where all players come together across their teams, and make a single, large choice about how to handle the event, which will affect one or more SDGs. There is no dice rolling or random chance involved in World Events - however, an event can either be Positive, Neutral or Negative.

There are three “event points” during the game - after round 2, after round 4, and after round 6. When the players reach an event point, the game will decide whether to play a Positive, Neutral, or Negative event.

- **Positive events** involve players choosing a path that gives progress to multiple SDGs, and loses progress to a single SDG as well.
- **Neutral events** involve players choosing a path that will give progress to one or two SDGs, and lose the same amount of progress from one or two different SDGs.
- **Negative events** involve players choosing a path that will lose progress from one or more SDGs. (The final negative event instead sees players losing progress from a large number of SDGs at the start, before choosing which ones to bring back up again. Mathematically, this is the same.)

The image shows a digital interface for a game event titled "PRIVATE CHARITY". The main screen displays a voting interface for 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). At the top, there is a progress bar with 17 slots, each containing a number (0 or 1) representing the number of votes for that SDG. Below the progress bar, the SDGs are listed with their corresponding icons and progress bars (e.g., 7/10, 4/10, 0/10, etc.). The interface includes a "Back" and "Next" button at the bottom.

A smartphone overlay on the right shows the mobile version of the interface. It displays the event title "PRIVATE CHARITY" and the team name "TEAM 2 Public Policy Analysts". The screen prompts the user to "Choose a path" and lists four options: "Top-Down Health Relief: 3 +5, 10 -5", "Direct Food Donation: 2 +5, 11 -5", "Financial Investment: 1 +5, 16 -5", and "Do Nothing". The "Top-Down Health Relief" option is selected and highlighted.

- When a World Event hits, players will have to vote together as one group on one of three (or sometimes four) possible paths. These are similar to the solutions found in the regular rounds, but only a single one will be implemented (the one the majority of players voted for). Event paths generally have larger consequences than solutions to individual problems, but an event will have a smaller impact than the total impact of all the solutions picked during a round, plus the impact of the outcome of that round (success or failure).

- Each positive, neutral, or negative path for a given event adds up to the same total progress gained – the choice is about what to prioritize.

The event will start with a short description of what has happened, framing the players' choices. Some events also have an "initial impact", which is usually a small effect (positive or negative) on a single SDG, which is applied immediately after receiving the event.

After players have chosen a path, they're given a short narrative description of the outcome, and their SDGs are updated. Then, play moves on to the next round.

We recommend not telling players about World Events ahead of time, and only explaining how they work when players encounter the first event. We also recommend not telling players about the positive, neutral and negative categories, or when later events will come up. The events are meant to feel naturalistic and surprising. It's fine for players to speculate about whether events are determined at random, or as consequences of their earlier choices. If they ask, tell them that there are other events they could have seen instead.

To learn how the game determines whether to play a positive, neutral or negative event, see "Balance".

Technical issues

Here we'll cover some technical issues which, while rare, may come up during play.

The participant screen has gone blank on a participant's device

- First, they should try to refresh the page in their browser. This should bring back the appropriate participant screen, corresponding to the facilitator screen you're currently on.
- If this doesn't solve it, check that the device is connected to WiFi or cellular data. Try to turn off WiFi on the device, if cellular data is available, and refresh the page again.
- If you're still unable to re-establish connection, have the participant close the browser window, and log in again. (Remember that you can bring the QR code and web address for the session back up by clicking the QR code button at the bottom left of the facilitator screen.)
- If they still can't re-establish a connection to the session, have them join through a different browser on their device, or on a different device altogether, if they have access to one.
- In all else fails, have the disconnected participant share a device with someone else

The facilitator screen has gone blank

- Try to refresh the page in your browser.
- Check your WiFi connection. If it seems bad or unstable, consider making a "hotspot" (temporary WiFi signal) with a device (such as your phone) with a stable cellular connection.
- Only start a new session (using the "start a session" link from the open access portal) if you have no other options - a new session will not have any connection to the original, which means you will have to play the game again from the beginning, and all participants will have to join again.

I can't move on from a page - nothing happens when I click the "Next" button

- This is most likely because a required interaction on the page has not been taken, which is blocking you from moving on. If this is the case, there will be a red popup in the upper right corner of the facilitator screen, detailing which interaction still needs to be taken, such as selecting an option to vote for. Try to do the interaction (or have at least one participant do it, if it's referring to an interaction on the participant screen), and try again.
- If there's no red popup, but nothing happens when you click the "Next" button, you unfortunately have to start a new session. This is very unlikely to happen.

Appendix

List of problems

Here follows a list of the game's 8 problems, together with their impacted SDGs, and the solutions each team has for each problem, for easy reference. Short term solutions are marked ST, and long term solutions are marked LT.

Problem 1: Collapsing Coral Reefs Impacted SDGs: 12, 13, 14				
Technology Developers	Public Policy Analysts	Community Coordinators	Business Council	International Collaborators
Early Warning Systems for Coral Bleaching (ST)	Regulate Coastal Development (ST)	Coral Reef Restoration Projects (ST)	Install Artificial Reef Structures (ST)	Establish Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) (ST)
Develop Heat-Resistant Coral Species (LT): 9 +2, 14 +2	Educate on Sustainable Fishing and Reef Conservation (LT): 2 +1, 4 +1, 11 +1, 14 +1	Sustainable Agriculture to Reduce Runoff (LT): 6 +1, 12 +1, 14 +1, 15 +1	Reduce Plastic Pollution (LT): 12 +2, 14 +2	Promote Renewable Energy Adoption (LT): 7 +2, 13 +2
Research Ocean Acidification Effects (LT): 2 +2, 14 +2	Ban Harmful Fishing Practices (LT): 11 +1, 14 +3	Restore Mangrove Forests (LT): 13 +2, 14 +1, 15 +1	Encourage Sustainable Tourism (LT): 8 +1, 11 +1, 12 +1, 14 +1	Limit Global Warming Agreements (LT): 13 +2, 17 +2

Problem 2: Ravaged Farm Lands Impacted SDGs: 2, 6, 11, 15				
Technology Developers	Public Policy Analysts	Community Coordinators	Business Council	International Collaborators
Biological Soil Crust Activation (ST)	Launch Drought-Resilient Seed Subsidy Programs (ST)	Rainwater Harvesting Techniques (ST)	Use of Treated Wastewater for Irrigation (ST)	Develop Early Warning Systems for Drought (ST)
Implement Drip Irrigation Systems (LT): 2 +1, 6 +2, 15 +1	Educate Farmers on Sustainable Practices (LT): 2 +1, 4 +2, 6 +1	Practice Conservation Tillage (LT): 2 +3, 15 +1	Develop and Use Biofertilizers (LT): 2 +1, 9 +1, 12 +1, 15 +1	Introduce Policies for Water Pricing and Allocation (LT): 6 +2, 12 +1, 17 +1
Implement Terracing and Contour Farming (LT): 2 +2, 15 +2	Promote Community-Based Water Management (LT): 1 +1, 6 +2, 16 +1	Agroforestry Practices (LT): 2 +1, 13 +1, 15 +2	Build Small-Scale Water Reservoirs (LT): 2 +1, 6 +2, 11 +1	Promote Drought-Resistant Crop Varieties (LT): 2 +2, 6 +2

Problem 3: Plastic-Choked Oceans Impacted SDGs: 12, 14				
Technology Developers	Public Policy Analysts	Community Coordinators	Business Council	International Collaborators
Deploy Ocean Surface Cleanup Drones (ST)	Implement Nationwide Plastic Bans (ST)	Support Community Clean-Up Programs (ST)	New Uses for Plastic Waste (ST)	Organize Ocean Clean-Up Initiatives (ST)
Implement Microplastic Filtration Systems (LT): 3 +1, 6 +2, 14 +1	Educate Public on Plastic Pollution (LT): 4 +2, 12 +1, 17 +1	Install Trash Capture Systems in Rivers (LT): 5 +2, 11 +1, 14 +1	Develop Ocean-Friendly Packaging (LT): 9 +2, 12 +1, 14 +1	Introduce Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) (LT): 9 -2, 12 +4, 14 +2
Invest in Waste-to-Energy Technologies (LT): 7 +2, 9 +2, 13 -1, 14 +1	Implement Deposit Return Schemes (LT): 11 +1, 12 +2, 14 +1	Improve Recycling and Waste Management (LT): 9 +1, 11 +1, 12 +2	Scale Ocean Plastic Certification and Branding Initiatives (LT): 9 +1, 12 +2, 17 +1	Strengthen International Waste Trade Regulations (LT): 12 +2, 16 +1, 17 +1

Problem 4: Polluted Air Crisis Impacted SDGs: 3, 7, 11, 13				
Technology Developers	Public Policy Analysts	Community Coordinators	Business Council	International Collaborators
Implement Smart City Technologies for Air Quality Monitoring (ST)	Implement Clean Air Zones (Low Emission Zones) (ST)	Transition to Electric and Free Public Transport (ST)	Retrofit Buildings for Energy Efficiency (ST)	Coordinate Rapid Air Quality Monitoring Networks (ST)
Support Research into Air Purification Technologies (LT): 3 +2, 9 +1, 11 +1	Incentivize Renewable Energy Adoption (LT): 7 +2, 11 +1, 13 +1	Encourage Urban Green Spaces (Plant Trees) (LT): 11 +2, 13 +1, 15 +1	Invest in Biofuels (LT): 2 -2, 7 +2, 9 +3, 13 +1	Enforce Emission Standards for Industries (LT): 3 +2, 12 +1, 13 +3, 17 -2
Implement Carbon Capture Technologies (LT): 8 +2, 9 +2, 13 +2, 16 -2	Phase Out Coal for Residential and Industrial Use (LT): 3 +1, 7 +2, 8 -2, 13 +3	Promote Cycling and Walking Infrastructure (LT): 3 +2, 11 +1, 13 +1	Expand Electric Vehicle Infrastructure (LT): 7 +1, 9 +1, 11 +2	International Agreements on Emission Reductions (LT): 3 +1, 13 +1, 17 +2

Problem 5: Digital Divide Impacted SDGs: 1, 4, 9, 10				
Technology Developers	Public Policy Analysts	Community Coordinators	Business Council	International Collaborators
Fund Scholarships for Tech Education (ST)	Create Low-Cost Mobile Internet Plans (ST)	Establish Public Wi-Fi Hotspots (ST)	Subsidize Affordable Digital Devices (ST)	Partnerships with Tech Companies for Device Donations (ST)
Leverage 5G for Urban and Rural Connectivity (LT): 9 +1, 10 +2, 11 +1	Digital Literacy Training Programs (LT): 4 +2, 5 +1, 8 +1	Subsidize Internet Access for Low-Income Families (LT): 8 +1, 9 +3	Expand Rural Broadband Infrastructure (LT): 9 +2, 10 +2	Lower Import Tax on Tech for Developing Countries (LT): 1 +3, 7 +1, 9 +2, 17 -2
Expand Fiberoptics Infrastructure (LT): 9 +3, 10 +1	Right to Repair for Digital Devices (LT): 9 -1, 10 +2, 11 +1, 12 +2	Build Community Tech Centers (LT): 4 +2, 10 +1, 11 +1	Free, Limited Internet Access (LT): 4 -2, 9 +3, 10 +2, 17 +1	Promote Legislation for Digital Equity (LT): 10 +1, 16 +1, 17 +2

Problem 6: Gender Wage Gap Impacted SDGs: 5, 8, 16				
Technology Developers	Public Policy Analysts	Community Coordinators	Business Council	International Collaborators
Mobile Apps for Career Advancement (ST)	Gender Parity Quotas (ST)	Invest In Women-Owned Businesses (ST)	Appoint Diversity Managers and Task Forces (ST)	Launch Gender Equality Awareness Campaigns (ST)
Tech Scholarships (LT): 4 +2, 5 +1, 9 +1	Conduct Regular Pay Audits (LT): 5 +2, 8 +1, 16 +1	Collective Bargaining (LT): 1 +1, 5 +2, 8 +2, 9 -1	Improve Flexible Working Conditions (LT): 5 +1, 8 +1, 10 +1, 11 +1	Strengthen the Equal Pay International Coalition (LT): 5 +1, 8 +1, 16 +1, 17 +1
Develop Pay Transparency Tools (LT): 5 +1, 8 +1, 9 +1, 16 +1	Raise Minimum Wage (LT): 1 +2, 5 +1, 8 +3, 9 -2	Strengthen the Care Economy (LT): 1 +1, 5 +1, 11 +2	Ban Use of Salary History in Hiring Decisions (LT): 5 +1, 8 +1, 16 +2	Promote Research into Gender Disparities (LT): 4 +1, 5 +1, 9 +1, 17 +1

Problem 7: Rural Healthcare Crisis Impacted SDGs: 3, 6, 10, 11				
Technology Developers	Public Policy Analysts	Community Coordinators	Business Council	International Collaborators
Telemedicine Services (ST)	Incentives for Healthcare Workers (ST)	Health Awareness Campaigns (ST)	Attract Outside Talent (ST)	Partnerships with NGOs for Rural Healthcare (ST)
Sustainable Energy and Water Systems for Rural Health Centers (LT): 3 +1, 6 +1, 7 +1, 11 +1	Invest in Rural Health Services (LT): 3 +2, 9 +1, 10 +1	Partner with Vulnerable Groups (LT): 3 +1, 5 +1, 10 +1, 11 +1	Targeted, Private Relief Partnerships (LT): 3 +4, 9 +2, 11 -2	Push for the Marginalized (LT): 3 +1, 5 +1, 10 +1, 16 +1
New Detection Methods (LT): 3 +3, 9 +1	Focus on Education and Training (LT): 3 +1, 4 +2, 8 +1	Increase Financial Stability and Independence (LT): 1 +1, 3 +1, 8 +1, 11 +1	Invest in Infrastructure (LT): 3 +1, 8 +1, 9 +1, 11 +1	Release Pharmaceutical Patents (LT): 1 +2, 3 +2, 8 +2, 17 -2

Problem 8: Education Access Inequality Impacted SDGs: 1, 4, 10, 17				
Technology Developers	Public Policy Analysts	Community Coordinators	Business Council	International Collaborators
Develop Multimedia Learning Materials (ST)	Provide Free School Meals (ST)	Set Up Community Learning Centers (ST)	Distribute Free Learning Materials (ST)	Provide Emergency Relief Education for Crisis Areas (ST)
Leverage Technology for Remote Learning (LT): 4 +1, 9 +3	Support Teachers Financially (LT): 1 +1, 4 +2, 8 +1	Invest in Infrastructure (LT): 4 +1, 9 +1, 10 +1, 11 +1	Train Youth in Employable Skills (LT): 1 +2, 8 +2, 10 -1, 11 +1	Promote Gender-Sensitive Education Policies (LT): 4 +1, 5 +1, 16 +1, 17 +1
Provide Scholarships for Marginalized Groups (LT): 1 +1, 4 +1, 5 +1, 10 +1	Equitable School District Funding (LT): 4 +3, 9 -2, 10 +1, 11 +2	Focus on Students with Special Needs (LT): 4 +2, 10 +2	Measure Efficacy of Learning Materials (LT): 4 +1, 9 +2, 17 +1	Partner with NGOs for Education Access (LT): 4 +1, 10 +2, 16 -1, 17 +2

List of World Events

Here follows a list of all possible events, as well as their initial impact, and the potential paths players can choose to take for each of them, for reference. The progress gained or lost is scaled with the number of players, and is given here as references, rather than actual numbers. For an in-depth explanation of these values, see “Balance: World Events”.

Event 1 After round 2			
Type	Positive	Neutral	Negative
Name	Coalition of the Willing	Fraught Compromises	Collaboration Breaks Down
Initial impact	+3 SDG 2nd to 17	-3 SDG 3rd to 17	-3 SDG 2nd to 17
Path 1	Protect Marine Life: +1 status to 14 +3 SDG 2nd to 2 -3 SDG 2nd to 8	Lower Emission Goals: +3 SDG 2nd to 9 -3 SDG 2nd to 13	Give Up on Enforcing Marine Protections: -1 status to 14
Path 2	Transition to Renewable Energy: +1 status to 13 +3 SDG 2nd to 7 -3 SDG 2nd to 9	Pressure Key Emitting Industries: +3 SDG 2nd to 13 -3 SDG 2nd to 9	Abandon Emission Goals: -1 status to 13
Path 3	Forgive Debt to Developing Nations: +1 status to 10 +3 SDG 2nd to 1 -3 SDG 2nd to 17	Focus on Growth in Developing Countries: +3 SDG 2nd to 8 -3 SDG 2nd to 10	Refuse Demands for Colonial Reparations: -1 status to 10
Path 4	-	Focus on Redistribution in Developing Countries: +3 SDG 2nd to 10 -3 SDG 2nd to 8	-

Event 2 After round 4			
Type	Positive	Neutral	Negative
Name	Emergency Relief	Private Charity	Disaster Strikes
Initial impact	+4 SDG 3rd to 1	+4 SDG 3rd to 17	-3 SDG 2nd to 15
Path 1	Focus on Health +1 status to 3 -3 SDG 2nd to 12	Top-Down Health Relief +3 SDG 2nd to 3 -3 SDG 2nd to 10	Focus on Infrastructure and Rebuilding -1 status to 3

Path 2	Focus on Hunger +1 status to 2 -3 SDG 2nd to 11	Direct Food Donation +3 SDG 2nd to 2 -3 SDG 2nd to 11	Focus on Health and Rebuilding -1 status to 9
Path 3	Focus on Long-Term Sustainability +1 status to 11 -3 SDG 2nd to 17	Financial Investment +3 SDG 2nd to 1 -3 SDG 2nd to 16	Focus on Infrastructure and Health -1 status to 11
Path 4	-	Do Nothing No effect	-

Event 3 After round 6			
Type	Positive	Neutral	Negative
Name	Progress Towards Peace	A Tentative Peace	War Breaks Out
Initial impact	+3 SDG 2nd to 16	+3 SDG 2nd to 16 -3 SDG 2nd to 17	-2 SDG 2nd to 3 -4 SDG 3rd to 9 -4 SDG 2nd to 11 -3 SDG 2nd to 16 -3 SDG 3rd to 17
Path 1	Health and Safety +3 SDG 2nd to 2 +3 SDG 2nd to 3 +3 SDG 2nd to 6 -3 SDG 2nd to 8	Emergency Relief +3 SDG 2nd to 2 +3 SDG 2nd to 3 -3 SDG 2nd to 9 -3 SDG 2nd to 11	Helping Refugees +3 SDG 3rd to 10 +3 SDG 3rd to 17
Path 2	Rebuilding +3 SDG 2nd to 8 +3 SDG 2nd to 9 +3 SDG 2nd to 11 -3 SDG 2nd to 10	Normalizing Diplomatic Relations +3 SDG 2nd to 16 +3 SDG 2nd to 17 -3 SDG 2nd to 3 -3 SDG 2nd to 10	Emergency Relief +3 SDG 3rd to 2 +3 SDG 3rd to 3
Path 3	Managing Tensions +3 SDG 2nd to 10 +3 SDG 2nd to 16 +3 SDG 2nd to 17 -3 SDG 2nd to 9	Rebuilding +3 SDG 2nd to 9 +3 SDG 2nd to 11 -3 SDG 2nd to 8 -3 SDG 2nd to 17	International Intervention +3 SDG 3rd to 3 +3 SDG 3rd to 10 +3 SDG 3rd to 16 -3 SDG 3rd to 17

Balance

This section is provided more as documentation for some of the game's less obvious mechanics, and is not necessary reading for facilitating the game. If you're wondering how certain numbers are determined, such as die size, the amount of progress necessary to advance an SDG to its next status, or the amount of progress gained or lost on success or failure, read on. In general, we recommend not sharing these values or calculations with players, to keep the game feeling more naturalistic.

Number of active teams

The number of teams in play determines almost all other values in the game, and will be referred to as # of teams from here. However, the impact of individual solutions are *not* scaled to the number of teams, since each team implements its own solution. The impact of a long term solution always totals to +4 progress, distributed across one to four different SDGs. Some solutions give negative impact to an SDG, which means that the positive impact on other SDGs becomes larger - it still always totals to 4.

Here is a breakdown of the different values affected by the number of teams:

# of teams	Die size	Necessary SDG progress	Target number	Starting SDG progress	Small starting progress modifier	Large starting progress modifier	Max effective short term solutions
2	4	4	4	0	0	1	1
3	6	6	5	1	1	1	1
4	8	8	7	2	1	2	2
5	10	10	8	4	1	2	2

Die size & necessary SDG progress

The die size is # of teams * 2. This number is also the amount of progress necessary to advance an SDG's status.

Target number

The target number players have to hit to succeed on a problem. This number is the same for all problems.

Starting progress

The standard starting progress on each SDG. If the starting setup is not randomized, all SDGs will start on this progress.

Small starting progress modifier

If the starting setup is modified, two random SDGs will gain this amount of progress, and two will lose this amount of progress.

Large starting progress modifier

If the starting setup is modified, two random SDGs will gain this amount of progress, and two will lose this amount of progress.

Max effective short term solutions

The maximum number of short term solutions that will add to the modifier for a problem. If more short term solutions are implemented on a problem than this, this number will be added to the modifier, rather than the number of short term solutions added.

Consequences of success and failure

The consequences of success and failure (how much progress on impacted SDGs is gained or lost if players solve vs. fail to solve a problem) are determined partially by the number of active teams, and partially during setup, where the facilitator chooses whether each of these should be "Normal" or "Large" (see "Setup"). This works as follows:

The number of impacted SDGs varies from problem to problem. However, the total amount of progress gained or lost is always the same (we can call this the total progress modifier). A normal consequence equals # of teams * 2 total progress modifier, and a large consequence equals # of teams * 3 total progress modifier.

The total progress modifier is then distributed across the different impacted SDGs - but not evenly. Some SDGs are more impacted by a problem than others. For each problem, its impacted SDGs are ranked, and are affected by success or failure depending on its rank. The sum of impact on all impacted SDGs equals the total progress modifier. The way progress is distributed across SDGs breaks down like this:

Normal consequences										
# of teams	Total progress modifier	2 SDGs: 1st	2 SDGs: 2nd	3 SDGs: 1st	3 SDGs: 2nd	3 SDGs: 3rd	4 SDGs: 1st	4 SDGs: 2nd	4 SDGs: 3rd	4 SDGs: 4th
2	4	3	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1
3	6	4	2	3	2	1	2	2	1	1
4	8	5	3	4	3	1	4	2	1	1
5	10	6	4	5	3	2	3	3	2	2

Large consequences										
# of teams	Total progress modifier	2 SDGs: 1st	2 SDGs: 2nd	3 SDGs: 1st	3 SDGs: 2nd	3 SDGs: 3rd	4 SDGs: 1st	4 SDGs: 2nd	4 SDGs: 3rd	4 SDGs: 4th
2	6	4	2	3	2	1	2	2	1	1
3	9	6	3	4	3	2	4	3	1	1
4	12	8	4	6	4	2	5	3	2	2
5	15	10	5	7	5	3	7	4	2	2

Example 1:

4 different teams are trying to solve the “Plastic-Choked Oceans” problem. They have consequences of success set to Normal (a total progress modifier of 8), and consequences of failure set to Large (a total progress modifier of 12).

“Plastic-Choked Oceans” only has 2 impacted SDGs: 14, which is ranked 1st, and 12, which is ranked 2nd. If players succeed on this problem, they will gain +5 to 14, and +3 to 12 (totaling 8). If they fail, they will get -8 to 14, and -4 to 12 (totaling -12).

Example 2:

3 different teams are trying to solve the “Polluted Air Crisis” problem. They have consequences of success set to Large (a total progress modifier of 9), and consequences of failure set to Normal (a total progress modifier of 6).

“Polluted Air Crisis” has 4 impacted SDGs: 7, ranked 1st, 3, ranked 2nd, 11, ranked 3rd, and 13, ranked 4th. If players succeed on this problem, they will gain +4 to 7, +3 to 3, +1 to 11, and +1 to 13 (totaling 9). If they fail, they will get -2 to 7, -2 to 3, -1 to 11, and -1 to 13 (totaling -6).

World Event balance

World Events exist as a balancing mechanic - players receive a negative event if they're doing well, a positive event if they're doing poorly, or a neutral event if they're in between. Specifically, which of the three available events to play is decided based on the players' performance *on the last two problems they faced*. If they failed both problems, they get the positive event; if they failed one and succeeded at the other, they get the neutral event; and if they succeeded at both, they get the negative event. We do not recommend making players aware of this, or even the fact that the Positive, Neutral and Negative categories exist.

For world events, both their initial impact, as well as the impact of the paths players choose for them, scales with the number of teams as well. In this way, world events work differently from regular solutions.

World events use the scaled consequences of success and failure described above for their effects in most cases. Sometimes, however, they give or remove as much progress as is necessary to advance a whole status. As an example, the initial impact of the first positive event, Coalition of the Willing, is +3 SDG 2nd to SDG 17, and the first path of the event, Protect Marine Life, gives +1 status to SDG 14, +3 SDG 2nd to SDG 2, and -3 SDG 2nd to SDG 8. To see what these values would be for a given number of teams, consult the table above (see "Balance: Consequences of success and failure").

For positive and neutral events, the values follow the Normal vs. Large scaling of *success* consequences - for negative events, they follow the scaling of *failure* consequences. A slight wrinkle to this is that, for positive and neutral events, both the values added and subtracted follow the scale of success consequences (the subtracted values are just subtracted). This is to balance them internally - for example, the Protect Marine Life path subtracts the same amount from SDG 8 as it adds to SDG 2.